

Effects of Turkey Bone Particulate on Mechanical Properties and Microstructure of Aluminium Brass

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Abstract

This work focuses on the influence of the addition of Turkey bone particulate (TBp) on the mechanical properties and microstructure of aluminium brass composite. Five different specimens of the Aluminium Brass with different percentages of TBp were considered. Hardness, impact, tensile and microstructural tests were carried out in order to determine the hardness, impact strength, tensile strength and microstructure of the composite respectively. The results of the tests show that the hardness increase from 104.8 VHN at 0% to 117.7 VHN at 4% as the percentage TBp is increased while the impact strength increases from 23.94 kJ/m² to 47.19 kJ/m². However, the ultimate tensile strength increase from 310.51 MPa to 401.81 MPa as the percentage TBp is increased from 0 to 4%. The microstructure analysis reveals a microstructure when 4% of TBp was added where both the α and β phases are uniformly distributed. It contains fine and packed grained structure which results to improved strength of the composite. This study provides useful information on specific areas of application where TBp-reinforced aluminium brass can be utilised.

Keywords: *hardness, impact strength, tensile strength, microstructure, turkey bone particulate, aluminium brass.*

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Introduction

Aluminium alloys are useful engineering materials being used in aerospace, marine and automobile industries due to their light weight,

resistance to corrosion, and high strength etc. One of the main advancement in material science over the last few decades has been the creation of relatively cheaper metal alloys

reinforced with waste, such as industrial, agricultural and animal wastes (Saravanan & Kumar, 2013). For instance, Aluminium alloys reinforced with ceramic particles exhibit improved mechanical properties compared to unreinforced aluminium alloys and more suitable for engineering applications (Callister & Rethwisch, 2015).

Many researchers have utilized different additives (in form of metal or animal waste) to improve the mechanical properties of Aluminium alloy. Adeyemi et al. studied the effects of cow horn particles on the hardness and impact value of Aluminium alloy (Gbenga Joshua et al., 2022). The results show that the reinforced composite has better hardness value compared the Aluminium alloy without reinforcement. Also, the impact value decreases as the quantity of cow horn added is increasing. The effects of cow horn particulates as an additive on the microstructure, tensile and compressive properties of recycled Aluminium alloy was investigated (Oguntuase et al., 2022). The results show that both the tensile and compressive strengths increase as the quantity of cow horn particulates increases. The influence of calcined snail shell particulate on mechanical properties of recycled Aluminium-Silicon alloy for automotive application was investigated (Kolawole et al., 2020). Waste snail shell was used for the study and the microstructure reveals fairly dispersed snail shell particulates in the Aluminium alloy matrix mixed with Aluminium-Silicon dendrites. The hardness, compressive, tensile and impact strength increased as the calcined snail shell particulate is increasing. The effect of reinforcing sand mould with coconut pod ashes on mechanical and micro-structural properties of Aluminium brass was investigated (G. J. Adeyemi et al., 2022). It was discovered that the mechanical properties of the brass increases as the percentages of the coconut ashes increase. The tensile strength and hardness decreases, whereas the ductility increases, as the concentration of the additive in the sand mould increases. Also, microstructural analysis showed increase in grain size as the concentration of additive in sand mould increased during casting which was due to decrease in cooling rate that

prolonged the time required for formation and solidification of the molten cast alloy.

Subrahmanyam et al., 2015 studied the effect of adding rice husk ash (RHA) and Fly ash (FA) to Aluminium composite (AlSi10Mg) in order to improve its mechanical properties. Different quantities of the RHA and FA were added to the alloy using liquid metal processing route. Different tests such as tensile, compressive strength, and hardness tests were carried out on the samples. It was discovered from the results that the tensile strength of the composite is found to be decreased when rice husk ash is increased and is maximum when fly ash and rice husk ash are taken each of 10% by weight. Increment in the quantity of RHA added increased the hardness of the composite while increment in the quantity of FA added decreased the hardness.

The effects of carbonized and uncarbonized eggshell particles on the microstructures and properties of Al-Cu-Mg/ eggshell particulate composites were investigated by Hassan & Aigbodion (2015). Properties like density, tensile strength, hardness values and impact energy of the composite were measured. The results of these tests revealed that using the carbonized eggshell as reinforcement in the Al-Cu-Mg alloy enhances better physical and mechanical properties than uncarbonized eggshell particles. The density was reduced by 7.4%, and tensile strength and hardness were enhanced 14.28% and 25.4%, respectively. The impact energy decreased by approximately 24.67% at 12% by weight of carbonized eggshell when compared to unreinforced AA2024 alloy.

However, some research works have been conducted on the use of another metal to improve the properties of aluminium alloys. An investigation was conducted to study the effect of Nickel addition on the mechanical properties of Aluminium bronze (Oluwadare et al., 2019). Five samples with varying Nickel composition (0-4%) were tested. The results show that increasing the quantity of Nickel improved the hardness, while tensile strength initially increased then decreased. Yaykaşlı & Göğebakan (2024) studied the influence of adding boron on the microstructure, thermal and mechanical

properties of Al-5%Mg-2%Ti Alloy. The results show that addition of boron to the aluminium alloy led to increase in hardness value and tensile strength. The images obtained using scanning electron microscope showed a brittle appearance due to boron added. The effect of magnesium on the mechanical properties and microstructure of a highly pure aluminium was studied by Gubicza et al. (2004). This was done over a wide range of strain and it was discovered that addition of magnesium has a strong effect on the recovery properties of the aluminium. As a result of this, the addition of magnesium significantly increases the dislocation density leading to an increment in proof stress over a wide range of strain. Also, addition of magnesium increases the strain which correspond to the formation of a stable microstructure. This occurs at high strains. The effect of adding tin on the mechanical properties of Aluminium bronze alloyed with 4 % Nickel was investigated by Oluwadare et al. (2024). The results show that the tensile strength of the alloy initially increases and subsequently reduced as the quantity of tin added is increasing. The hardness of increases as the quantity of tin is increasing. The effect of adding magnesium on the microstructure and mechanical properties of aluminium bronze was studied by Adeyemi et al. (2013). The experimental results show that addition of magnesium to aluminium bronze increases both the hardness and yield strength of the aluminium composite and reduces its ductility.

The focus of this study is to investigate the effect of turkey bone particulate on the mechanical properties and microstructure of Aluminium brass. Aluminium Brass is a typical example of Aluminium alloy formed by adding Aluminium to copper-zinc alloys. The mechanical properties of Aluminium Brass can be made better by adding one or more materials that is not expensive and readily available. One of such material is a turkey bone which is rich in calcium. The ingredients of turkey bones are organic materials and minerals. Examples of the mineral composition are calcium, potassium, magnesium, sodium, zinc, iron and phosphorus which are essential for the strength of bones (Williams et al., 2017).

In addition, collagen, a protein that offers durability and flexibility, is found in turkey bones. Collagen provides structural support to the extracellular space of connective tissues. The collagen-rich organic matrix may potentially interact molecularly with the metal matrix to affect mechanical properties.

Materials and Methods

Turkey bones (Fig. 1(a)) were obtained from a food store in Ado-Ekiti, while Aluminium and Zinc were sourced from Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. Copper was obtained from copper windings purchased from the market.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. (a) Washed and Sun-Dried Turkey Bones, (b) Grinded Turkey Bones Particulates

The bones were thoroughly washed with hot water so as to remove any trace of marrow, blood and other substances that can hinder proper bonding between the Aluminium brass and the additive, and sun-dried for about a month as shown in Fig. 1(b). The bone was then crushed with hammer in order to break into smaller pieces, and later grinded with a grinding machine as shown in Fig. 1(c).

The specimens were prepared using the sand-casting procedure. Wooden patterns shaped like the specimens were made. An integrated gating system was used to form the mould cavity inside the drag and cope assembly. Moulding sand, in its green state, was used to create sand moulds, which was then dried.

Figure 2. Crucible Pit Furnace

The Aluminium Brass alloy (with varying percentage of copper, 10% Aluminium, 2% zinc and 1–4% turkey bone particulate), were melted in a furnace (Fig. 2) and poured into a mould cavity. Copper was heated to 1085°C using

furnace at foundry workshop, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife Nigeria. The melting points of Aluminium and zinc are 660.30°C and 419.50°C, respectively, whereas copper has the highest melting point of all the metals at 1085°C.

The temperature of the molten metal in the crucible was measured by inserting the thermocouple through the opening in the furnace lid. Initially, the melting furnace was charged with copper, and a thermocouple was used. All other materials were added in accordance with their melting points such that Aluminium Brass and the ones reinforced with different proportion of TBp were formed. The different specimens produced were labelled specimen A to E, respectively. The control specimen which is a pure Aluminium Brass is labelled specimen A.

The cast specimen was allowed to cool down to room temperature and then ejected from the mould. The cast aluminium specimens were machined on lathe machine for hardness, tensile, impact and microstructural tests.

The hardness test specimens were machined to rectangular prism of 15 mm × 10 mm × 10 mm as shown in Fig. 3 (a). The impact specimens were machined to length of 60 mm, width of 10 mm, height of 10 mm and V notched angle of 45° to a depth of 2 mm (Fig. 3 (b)) while those used for tensile test are shown in Fig. 3 (c). The specimens were prepared to undergo tests after casting and machining into the required shapes (Fig. 4).

Table 1. Weight and Percentage Composition Ratio of Specimen

Specimen	Copper	Turkey-bone particulate	Aluminium	Zinc
A	440g (88%)	0g (0%)	50g (10%)	10g (2%)
B	435g (87%)	5g (1%)	50g (10%)	10g (2%)
C	430g (86%)	10g (2%)	50g (10%)	10g (2%)
D	425g (85%)	15g (3%)	50g (10%)	10g (2%)
E	420g (84%)	20g (4%)	50g (10%)	10g (2%)

Figure 3. Dimensions of Specimen for (a) Hardness Test (b) Impact Test

Figure 4. Different Specimens after Casting and Machining

pendulum was moved up to its locked position at a pre-swing angle of 160° and ensured it was locked. The specimen was placed in the Charpy Impact testing machine's vice so that the notch backing the hammer and is centered inside the vice, the pendulum was allowed to fall freely on the specimen and breaks the specimen. The safety considerations were reviewed before releasing the pendulum using the release mechanism. The Impact Energy (IE) absorbed was taken from the scale and recorded. The handle brake for the pendulum was pulled, and it returned to its locked position. The indicator at the topmost final position was subsequently read and recorded. The steps were repeated for all the specimens.

Experimental Procedure

Tests were conducted to determine how the addition of turkey bone particulates affect the microstructure and mechanical properties of reinforced Aluminium Brass. Charpy Impact Testing Machine, Vickers Hardness Testing Machine and Instron Universal Tensile Machine were employed to determine the mechanical properties of the composites.

Impact Test

The impact test of the specimens were carried out at room temperature using Charpy impact tester (Fig. 5) at the Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering Workshop Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

All safety guards were in place and the path of the swing for the pendulum was cleared. The

Figure 5. Charpy Impact Testing Machine

The impact strength (IS) of each specimen is determined using Equation (1)

$$IS = \frac{E}{A} \quad (1)$$

$$A = 2(lw + lh + hw) \quad (2)$$

where, $E, A, l, w,$ and h are the energy required to fracture the specimen, surface area of the specimen, length, width and height of the specimen respectively.

For this study, $l = 60 \text{ mm}, w = 10 \text{ mm}, h = 10 \text{ mm}.$

Hardness Test

A small indenter (a hard steel ball) is forced into the surface of the specimen. The depth of the penetration is measured and converted to a hardness number. The hardness tests were carried out at Engineering Material Development Institute (EMDI), Akure, Nigeria. The diameter of spherical indentation produced on the specimen after the indenter was removed was measured with an optical scanning system on the machine and converted to Vickers hardness value.. The procedure was repeated for all the specimens with different percentages of TBp.

Tensile Test

The tensile tests were carried out on the specimens at EMDI using a Universal Tensile Testing Machine. Both the computer and the testing machine are started and the software is set up. The specimen is loaded for testing. The results are retrieved from the data file after the test for further analysis. This procedure is repeated for all the specimens.

Microstructural Test

Microstructural examination was carried out on the specimens (Fig. 6) at EMDI. The specimens were grinded to have flat and smooth surface. Silicon carbide papers of grit size $220 \mu\text{m}, 320 \mu\text{m}, 400 \mu\text{m}$ and $600 \mu\text{m}$ were placed on the grinding machine. The grinding process was done under running water to wash away the grits

and also to avoid overheating. The specimens were rotated 90° between each grinding step to avoid scratches. Thereafter, a polishing cloth was placed on the polisher for the initial polishing, swamped with solution of one micron of silicon carbide. The final polishing stage was done using polishing cloth swamped with solution of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ silicon carbide until the surface of the specimen became a mirror-like. It is then washed and dried.

Figure 6. Specimen for Microstructural Test

Finally, the mirror-like surface specimens were etched in 2% NaOH, then put in a desiccator. They were viewed with optical metallurgical microscope (OMM) in order to reveal their internal structure.

Results and Discussion

Influence of Turkey Bone Particulate on Hardness of the Composites

The results of hardness test performed on the specimens A to E is presented in Fig. 7. The value of the hardness increase from 104.8 VHN to 117.7 VHN when the percentage composition of TBp in the Aluminium composite is 3%. . It is obvious that the hardness of the specimens increase as the percentage composition of the TBp are increased.

Figure 7. Effect of TBp on Hardness Properties of the Specimens

Influence of Turkey Bone Particulate on the Toughness of the Composites

Impact test was carried to evaluate the toughness of the composite to sudden load. It also shows the amount of energy absorbed by a material during fracture. The impact strength increase as the percentage composition of TBp added to the composites are increased (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Effect of TBp on Impact Strength of the Composite

Evaluation of Tensile Properties of the Composites

The tensile test data is displayed in the form of a stress-strain curve, which usually exhibits four distinct stages namely: stress corresponding to

the elastic limit, stress at the yield point, ultimate tensile stress (UTS) and breaking stress. The results of tensile test obtained from the aluminium brass reinforced with different percentages of the TBp are shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9. The Stress-Strain Curve

From the stress-strain diagram, it is very clear that that the ultimate tensile strength of the specimens increase as the % TBp is increased. However, this is not the case for specimen C whose ultimate tensile strength is 310.59 MPa while that of specimens B, D and E are 364.39, 398.71 and 401.81 respectively. Therefore, specimen E which has 4% of TBp (which has highest quantity of TBp) exhibits the highest ultimate tensile strength compared to all the specimens. The increase in ultimate tensile strength with increasing TBp is attributed to particulate agglomeration. However, at 4% of TBp added, improved particulate dispersion occurs.

Microstructural Analysis

The microstructure plays an important role for analyzing the distribution of distinct phases in an Aluminium composite. The microstructure was studied by using optical metallurgical microscope OMM as presented in Fig. 10 with magnification of $\times 100$.

The microstructural analysis of aluminium brass specimen with varying proportions of TBp reveals a significant impact on the material's microstructure. As TBp increases from 1% to 4%, the particulate distribution becomes more

pronounced, with a notable increase in particulate size.

Fig. 10 (a) shows the microstructure of aluminium brass without TBp. The β -phase (dark region) is distributed around the α -phase (light region) such that they are not uniformly distributed. The dark region is more pronounced in Figs 10 (b) and (c) when 1% and 2 % of TBp were added respectively but slightly different in (d) when 3% of TBp was added. The presence of dark region indicate low overall ductility of the composite (Pantazopoulos & Toulfatzis, 2012). Fig. 10 (d) shows a significant change in microstructure with particle growth, finer grains

such that particles start clustering together. Fig. 10 (e) shows the microstructure of the Aluminium composite when 4% of TBp was added. This reveals a microstructure where both the α and β phases are more distinct, pronounced and uniformly distributed. The hardness of the reinforced aluminium brass increased due to increment in the TBp atoms reducing the mobility of copper atoms. There is a substantial increase in particulate size and density. It contains fine and packed grained structure, resulting in enhanced strength and distinct brass color.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 10. Microstructures of (a) specimen A (b) specimen B (1% TBp) (c) specimen C (2% TBp) (d) specimen D (3% TBp) and (e) specimen E (4% TBp).

Conclusions

The effects of TBp on the mechanical properties and microstructure of Aluminium brass have been investigated. In general, the following are the conclusions drawn from the experimental results obtained.

- Turkey bone particulate, an agricultural waste, can be used to reinforce scraps aluminium brass thereby turning wastes into wealth and reduce environmental pollution.
- The results show that the hardness of the aluminium brass increases with addition of TBp.
- The impact strength of the reinforced aluminium brass increases with an increase in percentage of TBp in the composite.
- Increment in TBp addition to Aluminium brass alloy increases the ultimate tensile strength of the composite. The Aluminium brass with 4% TBp shows a better ultimate tensile strength when compared with alloy with 1%, 2%, and 3% of TBp.
- The Microstructural analysis reveals the presence of turkey bone particulate without the formation of any other inter-metallic compounds. It also reveals the absence of agglomeration of TBp in the metal matrix and

good bonding between TBp and the aluminium brass when 4% was added.

- TBp should be considered as a suitable additive to improve the mechanical properties of aluminium brass used to manufacture structural components of an airplane (e.g. landing gear) where high strength to weight ratio is required. It can also be added to reinforce aluminium brass used for manufacturing ship propellers in maritime applications.

Recommendations

For improvement on the present study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- Study the influence of TBp on corrosion resistance and tribological behavior of aluminium brass.
- The effect of TBp on thermal and electrical conductivities of aluminium brass should be determined.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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